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D6.2 – Smart Factory Testbed Setup – Final Results

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Executive Summary

This document comprises the deliverable D6.2 which describes the summarized results of the prototypical setup on the Multi-Agent System in the Smart Factory testbed demonstrator in the second iteration. The goal is to add further functions in the prototypical setup and to enhance the initial results of the architectural framework of MAS4AI in this testbed and to evaluate the subsequent results, based on the work packages WP2 – WP5 of the project and for other use case implementations in WP6 of the MAS4AI project.

We describe the Implementation of the MAS based on the Janus-Framework on further testbed examples, the Integration of the Agent Management System and the RDF-Functionalities and the examples for the Integration of Algorithms.

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1 Introduction

The main objective of the SmartFactory-KL Use Case follows the general objectives of WP6, to prove and validate the MAS4AI approach in industrial test beds. The modular Industrie 4.0 testbed of the Technology Initiative SmartFactory KL provides the possibility to build up, test and deploy the MAS approach combined with the prototypical development and implementation of defined agents with their requirements from WP 1.

The SmartFactory KL testbed provides the basis for the first functional prototype which is based on the MAS4AI architecture concept and consist of a modular production environment and the integration of message-based middleware solutions like OPC UA or the BaSyx-Middleware. The usage of several software components like discovery and registry services, which are essential in the testbed architecture, as well as the agent development and their configuration and execution is also considered in the context of the MAS deployment.

The development of the first prototypical MAS4AI implementation, which is documented in this document, follows several iterations. With each iteration, new components and features have been considered for interacting in the used MAS framework. The developments in the MAS framework Janus SARL, which is applied to the Smart Factory testbed to meet the requirements along predefined agent patterns, and the connection to physical hardware component for control purpose are presented as results of the first prototypical implementation.

The results of the second iteration consider on the requirements of agent types, which haven't been considered during the first iteration and furthermore focus on the integration of algorithms for machine learning as well for planning, and in general results for interoperable technology combination as well as configuration and parametrization of the agent system.

2 Scope of Smart Factory 1st testbed evaluation

2.1 Use Case Description

The SmartFactory-KL production environment consist of several demonstrator testbeds, in which the Production Level 4 (PL4) demonstrator of the DFKI has been developed and build up as modular skill-based factory testbed for modern automation hardware and software, as well as concepts.

The PL4 demonstrator as Cyber-Physical Production System (CPPS) consist of four Cyber-Physical Production Modules (CPPM) which encapsulate their capabilities to execute a defined production step with their own implemented skill interface. Each CPPM and the takeout place to receive the manufactured product is linked to the central rail system, which transports the workpiece carrier. The demonstrator environment is based on a service-oriented architecture [1] and can reconfigure the setup of CPPM with the plug-and-produce capability.

Figure 1: SmartFactory PL4 demonstrator with product

The modular setup provides a basis for distributed deployment for control and data collection in production environments with physical and virtual software assets, which should be integrated in scope of MAS4AI system validation. In the PL4 demonstrator, the product to be manufactured is modular as well and consist of several parts, which can be combined and ordered individually. The SmartFactory PL4 demonstrator with product is shown in Figure 1.

The production process of the PL4 demonstrator to produce this product follows the sequence as shown in Table 1. The processed sequence of the corresponding CPPM of the PL4

demonstrator is also described with relation to the production step. The several CPPM of the demonstrator, where each module is responsible to execute one step in the production process, is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Smart Factory KL – Process steps of the PL4 demonstrator

Process step	Short Description
Step 1	<p>Module 1: “StorageAndAssembly”</p> <p>Get the workpiece carrier with a pick and place from the current shuttle of the rail system into the production module.</p> <p>Pick a nubstone (in the ordered color) from the storage element and place (assemble) it on top of the base nubstone USB stick and set it onto the workpiece carrier.</p> <p>Set the workpiece carrier with a pick and place from the current module back to the shuttle of the rail system.</p>
Step 2 (optional)	<p>Module 2: “Quality 1”</p> <p>Image-based quality inspection of the assembled part. The image of the quality check is stored and uploaded for the following production module for data storage purpose.</p>
Step 3	<p>Module 3: “Data Refuel”</p> <p>Data-flashing of ordered data and the picture of the quality check module onto the nubstone USB.</p>
Step 4	<p>Module 4: “Quality 2”</p> <p>Final Image-based quality inspection of the product.</p>
Step 5	<p>“Takeout Place”</p> <p>Module to get the final manufactured product out of the production line.</p>

Table 1: Process steps and related resources of the PL4 demonstrator

2.2 SmartFactory CPPM and Hardware Basis

In this chapter, the Cyber-Physical Production Modules with listed hardware assets, which are also considered in the requirements document, are shown. Each CPPM is presented with an own figure and the related table for each module describes the hardware related components, the module consists of.

Module 1: “StorageAndAssembly”

Figure 3: Module "StorageAndAssembly" (Picture by A. Sell)

Type	Name	Manufacturer
Micro Controller	Arduino Nano	Arduino
Sensor (Camera)	IS8401C-363-50	Cognex
Actor (Gripper)	EHPS-16-A-LK	Festo
Switch	Ha-VIS eCon 3070GB-A-PP	Harting
Switch	Eagle 30 Industrial Security Router	Hirschmann
Sensor (Camera)	ISR-751	Keyence
Sensor (RFID Reader)	IQT1-F61-IO-V1	Pepperl & Fuchs
Actor	PSEN sl-1.0p 1.1 / PSEN sl-1.0fm	PILZ
Sensor	PSEN cs1.1p	PILZ
Linear Axis Gripper	Linear Axis Gripper (summarized)	Rexroth
PLC	SIMATIC ET 200SP Open Controller, CPU	Siemens
PLC	PRO MAX3 240W 24V 10A	Weidmüller
Touchpanel PC	SIMATIC IPC477E	Siemens

Table 2: Hardware components of module 1

Figure 4: Module "StorageAndAssembly" (Picture by A. Sell)

Module 2: “Quality 1”

Figure 5: Module "Quality 1" (Picture by A. Sell)

Type	Name	Manufacturer
Micro Controller	ArduinoNano	Arduino
Touchpanel PC	Panel PC 3100 Einbaugerät	B&R
Sensor (Camera)	acA1440-73gc	Basler
Plug	Smart Electrical Connector (SmEC)	Harting
IPC	HAIIIC MICA ETH ES	Harting
Interface Node	PeriNet PeriNODE	PeriNet / EATON
Actor	PSEN sl-1.0p 1.1 / PSEN sl-1.0fm	PILZ
Sensor	PSEN cs1.1p	PILZ
PLC	SIMATIC ET 200SP	Siemens
Switch	IES101G2SFPW	StarTech

Table 3: Hardware components of module 2

Module 3: “Data Refuel”

Figure 6: Module "Data Refuel" (Picture by A. Sell)

Type	Name	Manufacturer
Actor (Linear axis gripper)	Linear axis system (summarized)	Afag
Actor (Gripper)	EHPS-16-A-LK	Festo
Automation PC	APC3100	B&R
Micro Controller	Arduino Nano	Arduino
Profinet Koppler	X20	B&R
Plug System	HAN-Modular-System	Harting
Switch	Eagle 30 Industrial Security Router	Hirschmann
Controller	Servo Drive C1100	LinMot
Sensor (RFID Reader)	IQT1-F61-IO-V1	Pepperl & Fuchs
Actor	PSEN sl-1.0p 1.1	PILZ
Sensor	PSEN cs1.1p	PILZ
PLC	PNOZ m B1	PILZ
Touchpanel PC	SIMATIC IPC477E	Siemens

Table 4: Hardware components of module 3

Figure 7: Modules "Data Refuel" and "Quality 2" (Picture by A. Sell)

Module 4: “Quality 2”

Figure 8: Module "Quality 2" (Picture by A. Sell)

Type	Name	Manufacturer
Micro Controller	Arduino Nano	Arduino
Automation PC	APC3100	B&R
Profinet Koppler	X20	B&R
PLC	X20 System	B&R
Sensor (Camera)	acA1440-73gc	Basler
Switch	Eagle 30 Industrial Security Router	Hirschmann
IPC	Atlas 500	Huawei
Actor	PSEN sl-1.0p 1.1 / PSEN sl-1.0fm	PILZ
Sensor	PSEN cs1.1p	PILZ
Touchpanel PC	VR4215.1	Rexroth

Table 5: Hardware components of module 4

Furthermore, there are hardware assets, which are not related to the CPPM itself, for example the transport system. These components are listed in Table 6.

Type	Name	Manufacturer
Edge Cloud Server	OneCite	GEC / Rittal
Conveyor system	TracSet	Montratec
Conveyor system (planned)	ACOPOStrak	B&R
Tablet	Ipad	Apple
Smart Glasses	Hololens 2	Microsoft
Infrastructure Box	Infrastrukturbox	SmartFactory
ATV	Robotino	Festo
Manual assembly station	HAP	SmartFactory

Table 6: Hardware-related components and assets (1st Iteration)

2.3 SmartFactory Software Basis

The SmartFactory-KL testbed environment consists of various architecture components and communication protocols, that are described in this chapter. The overall architecture is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: SmartFactory architecture

Each CPPM of the PL4 demonstrator (production units and transport units), which are related to the edge level, consist of physical assets that are controlled by internal PLC that is connected to corresponding actors and sensors. The capabilities of each CPPM are implemented with a skill-based approach using OPC UA, that provides a uniform interface to control the CPPM and to get data from it.

The architecture consists of the Plant-Service level of several software components for setup of individual product design during creation of customer orders, the build-up of a recipe in the production configuration in terms of a production plan for the demonstrator and the production configuration for orchestration of the production process. Furthermore, an interface for smart worker assistance is provided, to connect with HMI devices.

For data exchange of pictures takes from the quality check, that can be uploaded to the product by using the “Data Refuel”-Module, an own FTP Server is available, which communicated with the modules OPC UA interface. The integration components take care about registry and discovery of CPPM skills (CPPM skill registry) and Plant services (Service registry) and provide furthermore a trusted cloud integration gateway. The communication protocols, related to their architecture components, are listed in Table 7.

Protocol	Architecture Component
OPC UA	Production Modules Production Flow Control HMI
MQTT	Cloud Applications Enterprise Resource Planning System
REST	Enterprise Resource Planning System Production Flow Control Production Design Production Configuration Registry (Skills and Topology) API Management Discovery
Profibus	Production Modules Infrastructure Nodes
FTP	Upload product pictures for quality control or for saving it on the product

Table 7: SmartFactory architecture components and protocols (1st iteration)

The services with security mechanisms are presented in Table 8.

Cloud Services	Comm.-Protocol	Security
IBM Cloud	IBM PSB	Authentication
Gaia X Connector	MQTT & IDS (HTTP)	Authentication (Certificates)

Table 8: Clouds and connectors (1st iteration)

2.4 Requirements Scope of first prototype

Based on the modular service-oriented architecture of the SmartFactory KL testbed, the basis for setup of corresponding Asset Administration Shells (AAS) and Digital Twins has been prepared. To enable interoperable interfaces for the testbed assets, each CPPM can be represented as I4.0-Component, that can be ensured by adding an AAS to it. The setup of AAS furthermore enable an agent interaction with the physical hardware layer, or to software services like planning software, and can be combined with knowledge representations for semantic interoperability. The AAS can thus be built by using a related software framework like the BaSyx-Middleware, or integrated in OPC UA directly, following the OPC UA companion specification for AAS.

In scope of MAS4AI, the representation of the described physical and virtual components in form of AAS or uniform interface descriptions is focused to ensure a connection, control and data exchange between the system and a MAS framework in general. The steps to make the testbed ready for an agent-control, adding semantic technologies and for further integration of planning and machine learning agents are in the scope of the first prototypical implementation.

Related to the requirements of the MAS4AI approach, the aspects of planning, quality check and human-machine interaction are essential in general. The scope of the current use case planning, this means consideration of the availability of required serviced during production as defined in the products recipe, thus should be enhanced to be able to react to changing situations or target functions (e.g., time, costs, quality, sustainability). An improved flexible integration of quality controls in combination with the agent's behavior and data from assets can help to detect weaknesses in the production process, which are leading for example to higher waste. Integration of HMI agents can help to support operators in manufacturing environments and setup decisions as part of a MAS system.

In the first iterations of the MAS4AI system setup and evaluation in the Smart Factory testbed environment, the focus was on initial build-up of components under consideration of the given physical and virtual assets to be integrated. The requirements for this setup, related to the agent types in MAS4AI, that should be considered in these iterations are integrated mainly for resource agents and infrastructure purpose.

To fulfil the MAS4AI objectives, a list of the foreseen agents that should be considered during implementation and evaluated with their corresponding types is shown in Table 9. This list contains agent types, based on collected requirements in WP1 and is considered also in the first iterations of the Smart Factory testbed demonstrator evaluation.

Agent	Type
Local planning agent	Production planning
Resource agent	Resource
Production module agent	Resource
Transport agent	Resource
Quality inspection agent	Quality inspection
Safety agent	Safety
HMI agent	HMI
Energy agent	Resource
Infrastructure agent	Information
Data collection agent	Information
Product agent	Product

Table 9: SmartFactory: overview of expected agents and their types (1st iteration)

Related to several domains of the use case requirement analysis, the following scope has been defined for the Smart Factory use case.

Agent name	Description	Domain
Local planning agent	The local planning agent can perform job-shop scheduling with a limited number of machines and interaction with a global planning service.	Time, Flexibility
Quality Inspection agent	The quality inspection agent able to perform a classification of products based on defects and a classification of defective products based on the possibility of repair.	Sustainability, Quality
Production module agent	Production module agents have the possibility to interact with corresponding assets on the shop flow in the manner of resource agents.	Time, Flexibility
HMI agent	The HMI agent is an agent with interfaces to data visualization and database services.	Human Machine Interaction

Table 10: Categorization of agents (1st iteration)

Furthermore, transport agents have specific requirements, following aspects of safety, reliability, energy management that have impact to their communication and information.

A list of expected physical interactions between agents and the process environment is also presented in Table 11. For the proposed prototype development and evaluation, the implementation of production module agents as well as transport agents are mainly in focus of the setup.

Agent	Input	Output
Production module agent	Raw material	Processed material
Transport agent	Transported good	Transported good
Quality Inspection agent	Product	Product (+Quality assessment)
Energy agent	Energy	-

Table 11: SmartFactory: expected physical interactions between agents and their environment (1st iteration)

The list of special considerations for agents related with ethics or trustworthiness are presented. Due to the focus of the first iterations prototype, the following aspects are not mainly focused.

Agent	Special Considerations
Safety agent	Safety regulations
HMI agent	Trustworthiness, Usability / accessibility
Data collection agent	Ethics (privacy rights, legal...)
Product agent	Reliability, Privacy, Trustworthiness

Table 12: SmartFactory: special considerations (1st iteration)

Predefined agent communication, which is based on the identified agent types, is necessary to setup the main interactions between several agent types with events and the related message syntax and semantics, following the approach of standardized conversion. The deployment of agents in the SmartFactory workflow, as it is expected to meet the requirements, together with the corresponding links between agents that are expected to interact within the process, is presented in Table 13.

Local planning agent	Task scheduling data. Process-related time to fulfil production orders. Other data needs to be assessed during the MAS4AI project.
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Quality Inspection agent	Picture and configuration criteria for batch size 1 quality control. “Ground truth” Data of the correct product configuration.
Production Module Agent	Sensor and Actor Data of the corresponding Modules in OPC UA – with properties and operations (as skill-based approach) Each current module states Skill-related time and energy data and their sequences Data about current configuration
HMI Agent	Status of the production orders Status of the production modules Machine data Database containing component documentation Information about the current operator

Table 13: Required agent data (1st iteration)

The overall interactions of these agents are visualized in Figure 10, considering resource agents, which are mainly in the scope of the first prototypical implementations, as well as the connection and data exchange with other agent types.

Figure 10: SmartFactory: agent-based workflow (1st iteration)

The interactions of each agent types, following the given overall setup, is also listed in Table 14.

Agent	Interaction mechanisms
Local planning agent	Local planning agents: Planned schedule Product agents: type, processing step, location, deadlines Production module agents: Skills, availability, key processing indicators Quality inspection agents: Defect products Energy agents: Energy prices, adjust machine performance Infrastructure agents
Resource agent (incl. Production Module agent, Transport agent, Quality inspection)	HMI agent (to interact with humans) Safety agent (safety assessment, human interaction) Energy agent (collect energy needs, (optional) adjust performance, (optional) alter state (standby, offline, etc.)) Data collection (collects data from resource agent)
Safety agent	HMI agent (show safety level, safety information, interaction with / location of operators) Data collection agent (sensors/actors, create protocols)
Energy agent	Product agent (fill lifecycle file) Data collection agent (report energy consumption)

Table 14: SmartFactory: Interactions between agents and associated requirements (1st iteration)

2.5 Method for Prototype Development

The Smart Factory prototype development and evaluation for the MAS4AI framework follows an iterative software prototyping approach, with goal of validation of the WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 results of the given project. The setup of the MAS is therefore based on a MAS framework in combination with a message-based middleware solution, like Apache Kafka and BaSyx, but also considering industrial Internet-of-Thing's web service technologies like HTTP, MQTT and OWL.

The prototyping therefore is considering the following aspects into the iteration's development and prototype evaluation:

- a. Digital twin preparation and integration with the AI agents for early assessment,
- b. pilot setup that involves integration of existing legacy systems,
- c. execution and validation of the individual agents and
- d. execution and validation with the whole MAS4AI system

During the prototype setup and implementation, the main requirements for the given context are considered. This includes the consideration of protocols to let the agents communicate with each other in the MAS framework environment, as well as the interaction with the shopfloor environment. Therefore, the build-up of digital twins and AAS is necessary for further integration, also for activities towards AI agents.

The development considers the integration of available legacy systems, as presented as physical CPPM of the Smart Factors PL4 demonstrator. The software components on the factory services and integration level, like Registry and Discovery, must also be considered in an iterative method.

The setup of the agent is following the agent type definition which has been presented on basis of the MAS4AI requirements analysis. For the first prototypical iterations, the integration of the resource agents is focused. For following iterations, the prototypical implementation will be enhanced with the agent types of the requirements list.

An implementation in the Smart Factory demonstrator does also consider the components and approaches of the MAS4AI work package contents for demonstration and evaluation purpose. This means, that during the software prototype setup, new components must be integrated and evaluated into a given MAS prototype state. Therefore, the addition of new components as well as interfaces, can be considered by using an iterative development method.

3 Iterative MAS4AI-Prototype Development

The MAS4AI prototype development for the PL4 Line followed several iterations to make the assets of the demonstrator available for agent’s interconnection and communication. After completing a defined iteration, the next build of the prototype has been focused.

3.1 1st Iteration – Setup first AAS and connect one transport agent to its asset

In the first iteration, the considered assets of the demonstrator (at first only the transport asset) have been analyzed and prepared towards build-up of AAS. Given predefined interfaces of the assets which can also be parametrized, the middleware level and MAS level must be prepared for setup of the AAS.

Figure 11: First iteration prototype

In case of the Smart Factory PL4 demonstrator, the interface on asset level comes with a skill based OPC UA interface. As middleware solution, the BaSyx-Middleware has been used. For the MAS-System the Janus SARL environment is used, setting up an initial agents’ configuration of simulated production modules as resource agents, which are calling for transport system. Furthermore, one transport agent has been prepared, also as resource agent, to consider the simulated requests from the production modules and to control the shuttle asset respectively.

For the first prototype iteration, the focus was on connection and control of the transport system, the PL4 line rail shuttle system. The goal was mainly to enable a general setup configuration in the BaSyx-Middleware to build up an AAS for the shuttle asset and then to setup the connection to its related OPC UA interface, by using the OPC UA adapter of BaSyx. The focus on this first iteration was, to enable an asset control out of the selected MAS system.

Given the proposed MAS4AI framework approach, the middleware and MAS level does not focus on predefined technologies or frameworks but have to offer the required functions which are related to their level. This means, that other middleware solutions or software components can be used, to setup a MAS-System or build up AAS and interconnection to the asset level. The given approach of the first MAS4AI implementation in the Smart Factory testbed therefore consider on open-source software frameworks, which comes with a suitable setup and functional scope for the proposed use case requirements.

In the middleware level, the assets of the demonstrator are represented with own AAS and submodel “Control Component”, that is used for the dispatch of AAS methods from a central or decentral controller. The AAS of the considered assets are registered in the BaSyx-Registry and the related endpoint information of the AAS is stored there already. The communication towards the assets is done with a OPC UA adapter, which depends on an interface configuration for the focused asset.

The AAS submodel contains properties and capabilities of the asset, like information about their current state, based on available state machines. The capabilities are implemented on the asset-level as related skills with the uniform OPC UA interface. If a request is sent to the AAS submodel, the BaSyx-Middleware process the information towards the field device adapter, which in this case is connected by using the OPC UA protocol. A predefined mapping-configuration between AAS submodel elements (like properties and operations) to their asset related OPC UA node is used in the adapter.

In the MAS system of Janus, one resource agent that represents the first production module, one resource agent that is representing the transport system and one HMI agent has been prepared. The request for transportation goes to the HMI agent, which refuses the given request because he is not able to process it, and to the transportation agent. The transport agent acknowledges the request, search the endpoint of the shuttle AAS inside of the BaSyx registry and process the AAS method, resulting in a shuttle control towards the requested position of the resource agent. After the request has been processed successfully, the information has been sent back to the resource agent, which have sent the request.

3.2 2nd Iteration – Setup holonic resource agents for production module sequence

The main goal of the second iteration was to enhance the control of the integrated transport shuttle in the MAS system. Resource agents are setup for each production module asset, which included the “Storage and Assembly” module, the “Quality 1” module, the “Data Refuel” module and the “Quality 2” module. Each of these agents simulated their actions in a default production process in the PL4 line. A PL4 demonstrator factory holon has been setup to let the given agents of this prototype iteration spawn. Each simulated resource agent, that stands for a production module, has the goal to send a request towards the shuttle agent, resulting in a related request to the shuttle asset.

Figure 12: Second iteration prototype

The resource agents, as simulated production modules, are requesting the shuttle agent for transport in a predefined process sequence of a PL4 line default process. The shuttle agent considers the requesting resource agent, and the requester data is also sent to the shuttle assets AAS. The adapter processes the information, resulting in a different parametrization which is sent to the related skill interface (another shuttle gate that should be reached from the asset). In this example, the resource agents are communicating with each other, to process in sequence. In the given process, the shuttle was able to reach the position of each production module with agents, leading to a full integration and request-related dynamic control of the transport agent with its asset’s parametrization.

Figure 13: Shuttle Transportation of second iteration

3.3 3rd Iteration – Setup assets with AAS and agents for process execution

The main goal of the third iteration was to setup the AAS for all production module and to integrate them in the BaSyx-Middleware. For each production module, the related resource agent in the MAS system is setup and the related agent behavior is developed. In this step, the first functional integration on the middleware layer has been used and adapted for each of the production modules, which are now coming with at least equal or more complex capabilities (e.g., assembly or data refuel), compared with the transport system.

In this step, the first functional integration on the middleware layer with the transport shuttle has been used and adapted to each of the production modules, which are coming with equal or more complex capabilities (e.g., assembly or data refuel), which now must be represented as resource agent behaviors and capabilities. Therefore, the behavior and capacity patterns of the Janus framework could be adapted, to encapsulate and use the predefined behavior-specific capacity functions with the related AAS communication.

An AAS with “Control Component” submodel thus has been setup for each production module asset, which included the “Storage and Assembly” module, the “Quality 1” module, the “Data Refuel” module and the “Quality 2” module. The OPC UA adapter in the BaSyx Middleware has been prepared to use several configurations, to dispatch AAS events and data (like operations call or property updates) with resource-related parametrization to the respective OPC UA node of the intended asset.

Figure 14: Third iteration prototype

The agents in the MAS system are now able to process the sequence like in the prototype of the second iteration but have now the possibility to control the production process with production steps and transportations in the physical demonstrator environment.

Figure 15: Shuttle Transportation of Production Modules AAS of third iteration

3.4 4th Iteration – Integration of planning component and AAS also for agents

The main goal of the fourth iteration was to integrate a component to let the resource agents work on a predefined planning. The holonic agent for the PL4 line must be able to provide data for planning purpose and to adapt production plans more flexible with current agents' behavior. Based on the results of the third iteration prototype, it is possible to process a full production sequence in the demonstrator, but due to the predefined sequence of this iteration, the agent's communication follows also predefined patterns.

Figure 16: Fourth iteration prototype

With the adaption of a plan, it is possible to change the current production and communication pattern more towards flexibility and reconfiguration of production units. Furthermore, a more flexible reaction due unforeseen events can be provided, for example if one production module has an error. Inside the factory holon, agents then can communicate and try to solve the problem, searching for other resource agents which can fulfil the action of the module that is not available anymore.

Related to the demonstrator setup, it is possible to schedule a plan for the PL4 demonstrator holon, and instead of quality check of the module “Quality 1” and then “Quality 2” the quality checks should be done twice by using the same quality module, for example if the quality of the check could for a given product could only be done with one of these modules. Otherwise, in case

of error of one quality module, for example if “Quality 2” cannot be used, it is possible to adapt the predefined plan and then search for alternative modules. In this case, an alternative option would be module “Quality 1”, or also the HMI agent, if a worker is available and can do the quality check manually.

The adaptation of a production plan comes also with the requirement of integration of a local planning agent. The integration needs the availability of AAS models for the current agent types and the possibility to host them in the BaSyx-Middleware, as well to register them in the registry. The starting and registration of holonic agents as well as their agent types furthermore requires the integration of an RDF-Store because the lack of the BaSyx-Registry for AAS to store more information than the endpoint information. This information is essential to search for suitable AAS as well during the initial start of holonic agents as well as for reconfiguration purpose.

The prototypical implementation of the fourth iteration is described in this document for the purpose reconfiguration and is currently in development and evaluation in the Smart Factory testbed. This iteration focuses on reconfiguration and adaptation to a plan, as well to build up this reconfiguration due to the error of one of the quality modules. The integration of the RDF-Store as well as planning and quality check agents also are a good possibility to evaluate the MAS4AI WP3, WP4 and WP5 approaches. Results of this integration and further MAS4AI framework evaluation will thus be considered in future research.

4 Smart Factory MAS4AI Implementation

The Smart Factory testbed implementation of the MAS4AI framework follows the proposed setup and content of the work packages. The structure is presented in Figure 17.

Figure 17: MAS4AI Framework

Related to the main aspects, the Smart Factory testbed demonstrator focused on topics:

- Implementation and evaluation of the MAS4AI setup as proposed in WP2
- Create a holonic representation for the existing (legacy) PL4 Demonstrator
- Integration of message systems like Apache Kafka for external communication of agents and communication or data collection of assets in a distributed environment
- Flexible integration at the AAS layer, for example by using BaSyx-Middleware or OPC-UA usage for real-time purpose on station level (e.g., also combined approach)
- Integration of RDF-Store for AAS semantic annotation as well as for requests during the start of the system
- HMI-Integration for system configuration and maintainer support

The holonic setup of the MAS4AI framework, as proposed in WP2, is presented in Figure 18. A holonic agent represents an entity, that can be deployed in a distributed environment and comes with an own AAS, in which the configuration and parametrization of underlying agent types inside this holon can be stored. A holonic agent in this way can thus consist of an own MAS, in which all related agents could be created and configured. An example of such an holon could be the resource holon of the Smart Factory PL4 demonstrator line, consisting of several resource agents that are controlling the production modules as well as the transport assets. Inside such a holon, also other agent types could be deployed, like quality agents as well as (local) planning agents for example.

Figure 18: MAS4AI Holonic Setup

The agent types are integrated as agent patterns, which are setup in common MAS frameworks like Jade or Janus. Nevertheless, the concept of MAS4AI considers a framework-independent approach, so that the agent types and their communication could be setup in similar way also in other MAS.

The agent interaction language is used in the first prototypical implementations by using the Janus agent communication mechanism. The approach to use framework-mechanisms is useable if all agents of an holon are setup and active in a same runtime environment. If the (holonic) agents are deployed on distributed hardware (e.g., if agents are deployed on machines or some AI agents are deployed in several cloud environments), the connection to a central message communication system like Apache Kafka is needed for data exchange and communication.

The interaction of agents with hardware or software components can be realized by using the AAS, providing predefined interfaces by using for example the BaSys-Middleware or OPC UA.

4.1 AAS and Digital twin preparation

Related to the MAS4AI holonic setup, the preparation and setup of AAS or digital twins is necessary for the integration into the MAS4AI framework. This part of the framework is represented in the “Data / AAS Layer” and is necessary to build up a virtual representation of the manufacturing environment. In the use case of the Smart Factory PL4 line, this also considers physical as well as virtual assets.

The physical assets, in form of CPPM, are integrated and represented as AAS into the BaSyx-Middleware. Therefore, the setup of several elements in the BaSyx-Middleware has been done, which should be considered here. The implementation of the AAS has been done with the BaSyx-Middleware. The related software elements of the middleware which are used for integration and representation of an asset with the AAS are presented in the Figure 19. For the AAS preparation, the BaSyx-Middleware [2] in Java is used with version 1.02.

Figure 19: Technical objects of BaSyx Middleware

The process of processing events, which are sent to the AAS, and data which can be got from the system, is described from a top-down view, introducing the used components with their role in the prototype.

If an agent of the MAS-System, for example a resource agent needs to find an AAS of an asset, they will investigate the BaSyx Registry to get the related endpoint. If an AAS is found, then the agent can perform a HTTP Rest-Call towards the AAS with corresponding parameters. Parameters

could be the agent ID, for example to lock the asset access for the given agent and to avoid that another agent can interact with this asset for control purpose. In case of the shuttle AAS, the information about the destination of the shuttle request must be set.

The assets AAS with the submodel “Control Component” is stored in the Registry [3] and is hosted by using a BaSyx AAS Server [4]. The integration and processing of events inside the BaSyx-Middleware can be performed by using the “Control Component” pattern [5], or by needs of data acquisition from shop floor devices, also with a “Device Integration” object which provides the connectivity with the required protocol of the asset [6].

```

JSON Rohdaten Kopfzeilen
Speichern Kopieren Alle einklappen Alle ausklappen JSON durchsuchen
submodelElements: {}
1:
  parent:
    keys:
      0:
        idType: "IRDI"
        type: "AssetAdministrationShell"
        value: ""
        local: true
    semanticId:
      keys:
        0:
          idType: "IdShort"
          type: "Submodel"
          value: "ControlComponentTemplate"
          local: false
    identification:
      idType: "Custom"
      id: "ControlComponent"
      idShort: "ControlComponent"
      kind: "Instance"
      dataSpecification: []
    modelType:
      name: "Submodel"
      embeddedDataSpecifications: []
    submodelElements:
      Occupy:
        parent:
          keys:
            0:
              idType: "Custom"
              type: "Submodel"
              value: "ControlComponent"
              local: true
          inputVariables: []
          idShort: "Occupy"
          kind: "Instance"
          outputVariables: []
        inunkah1a:

```

Figure 20: BaSyx-AAS example of the “Control Component” submodel as JSON file ¹

To collect data from the shopfloor level, data update programs can be setup in BaSyx to collect data on the AAS level or to get data directly from a virtualized related object (e.g., from “Control Component” or “Device Integration” object). The AAS and the objects in BaSyx are

¹ Asset Administration Shell JSON-Serialization in Web-Browser

working with the concept of the virtual automation bus (VAB) [7], so that collected data in this bus can be used to update AAS but also to store this data into several databases, using the BaSyx-Connectors.

The connection towards the shop floor device can be done with a “Control Component” or also “Device Integration” object in the runtime. Therefore, an adapter like OPC UA must be integrated into these objects, to process events and to get data from the asset. In this place, the integration of a mapping or configuration file was very helpful for the flexible integration of the Smart Factory prototype, so that events towards the AAS submodel can be translated into the related OPC UA node and to transform given parameters into the suitable OPC UA parameter set.

4.2 Pilot setup with integration of existing legacy systems

The prototypical implementation needs to consider the integration of legacy systems of the Smart Factory testbed environment. Related to the holonic approach of MAS4AI, legacy systems are categorized into a holonic level.

Figure 21: Pilot setup with integrated legacy systems as holons

At enterprise level, several software components should be considered for integration. These consist of ERP system, the global planning component, the product configuration for setup of suitable recipes for product orders, the material handling, and the production flow unit, which has the possibility to orchestrate the PL4 demonstrator environment. These services should be integrated under a common factory holon, interacting with related agent types.

On the level of production lines, a holon could be setup for the PL4 demonstrator holon which controls the production modules of this resource holon as well as the shuttle transport system. This holon already considered the integration of these legacy systems with the proposed iterative prototyping approach. Another holon for further testbed validations is currently setup and comes with a reconfigurable production module setup and shuttle-based transport system integration. These components should also be integrated in the MAS4AI evaluation of the Smart Factory testbed environment.

The legacy assets itself, represented with PLC devices, should be integrated by using middleware solutions like BaSyx.

4.3 Execution and validation of the individual agents

The implementation results of the first Smart Factory demonstrator example focus on the setup of the MAS system by using the MAS framework Janus which is based on the agent-oriented programming language SARL [8] and the Data / AAS layer of the BaSyx-Middleware. As presented in the prototypical development in the previous chapter, the iterative integrated components based on the MAS4AI framework setup as proposed in WP2.

Static holon	<p>Pattern for static holons, of the MAS4AI approach. The static holon takes care about initial setup and spawning of related agents.</p> <p>This object represents the structure for all lower-level static holons and manage the lifecycle of all related agents inside. The static holon thus can start a lifecycle for agent types, for example new resource agents.</p>
Agent-Types	<p>Resource-Agents like agents for production modules as well as for transport assets are considered. These agents can connect to the assets AAS and perform actions and read data from the asset.</p> <p>An HMI agent has also been considered for maintenance purpose, but not implemented with an HMI interface.</p>

Table 15: Implemented agent patterns inside the prototype

In Janus, a holonic agent is setup to perform all related resource agents for the Smart Factory use case. In this case, the HMI-agent, and the resource agents and transport agent spawns with a unique identifier.

Figure 22: Static holonic agent in the prototype setup ²

The start of the holonic agent can be done by using the Run configuration setting of the Janus Framework [9], which enables the start by using Janus tools and the default Java command line.

Figure 23: Janus Launch Configuration of holonic agent ³

² SARL IDE (Project Setup and Holonic Agent)

³ SARL IDE (Janus Launch Configuration)

Each agent in this context can setup his own behavior and integrate capabilities and skills of the Janus framework. Each of these objects can be defined as own Janus object. The communication between agents can be processed by using the internal Janus message system with predefined events [10].


```

1 package events
2
3 /**
4  * Definition of Transport events
5  */
6
7 event Move {
8 }
9
10 /* Each production asset has the possibility to call shuttle move */
11
12 event NeedToMoveShuttle {
13     var Requester : String
14 }
15
16 event ShuttleMoveDone {
17     var Requester : String
18 }
19

```

Figure 24: Transport events in SARL ⁴

An event can consist of internal syntax and of variables and objects. Events can be sent inside an agent, for example to start internal behavior, but can also be used to communication with other agents, if they have joined a predefined message channel [10]. In case of distributed MAS4AI agent deployment, the command line for subscription to internal message channels must be replaced with a callback to an integrated external messaging system, like Apache Kafka.

```

comspace = defaultContext.getOrCreateSpaceWithSpec(typeof(OpenEventSpaceSpecification),
    defaultContext.getID as UUID)

comspace.register(asEventListener())

/* Send BehaviorInitialize event in the agents internal context
*/

wake(new BehaviorInitialize => [AgentName = name])

```

Figure 25: Event listener of Janus message channels ⁵

⁴ SARL IDE (Transport events)

⁵ SARL IDE (Event listener)

An agent furthermore has the possibility to react to events in the scope of the agent definition or inside of active behaviors. Inside the Janus framework, these sorts of events are also needed, if an external messaging system should be used.

```

on Move {

    /* Meet precondition requirements from other agents.
     * In this case: Request transport capability.
     */

    info(agentname + ": Move request for shuttle")

    this.comspace.emit(new NeedToMoveShuttle => [Requester = agentname])

}
    
```

Figure 26: Event-Trigger inside of Janus agents ⁶

The communication between agents and inside of an agent object is presented in the Figure 27, showing a communication of several agents, that have been started inside an holonic agent.

```

<terminated> HolonicAgent (MAS4AI) [SARL Agent] C:\Program Files\AdoptOpenJDK\jdk-8.0.292.10-hotspot\bin\javaw.exe (14.03.2022, 20:37:42)
Command line parameters: [Ljava.lang.String;@7a32ef1
[INFORMATION, 8:37:44pm, AGENT-3ffd3cb8-54a7-4650-bd70-dfaf4bea0d37] Holon is active now and is spawning all belonging agents!
[INFORMATION, 8:37:44pm, AGENT-5dd23157-e134-4ead-9568-09357b1267a7] The maintainer agent with name Maintainer in active now!
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-994fcbf3-4d7d-4150-b171-fae2ce93135b] Installing the skill
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-994fcbf3-4d7d-4150-b171-fae2ce93135b] The transport agent with name Transport in active now!
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] The Module with name Assembly is active now!
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Installing the skill
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Installing the skill
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-c6f87865-9ec0-4a6a-8d9b-934f44c88999] The Module with name QS1 is active now!
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-c6f87865-9ec0-4a6a-8d9b-934f44c88999] Installing the skill
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: Ticker Behavior initialized
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: Assembly Behavior initialized
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-a1462f10-d4d5-45d8-824b-575c4ed33263] The Module with name DataStorage is active now!
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-a1462f10-d4d5-45d8-824b-575c4ed33263] Installing the skill
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker reached with value 1000
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-a1462f10-d4d5-45d8-824b-575c4ed33263] Installing the skill
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker reached with value 2000
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker reached with value 3000
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker reached with value 4000
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker reached with value 5000
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker reached with value 6000
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker reached with value 7000
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-2eb29ff7-d890-42b7-baa3-c88c3bdecf4c] The Module with name QS2 is active now!
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker reached with value 8000
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-2eb29ff7-d890-42b7-baa3-c88c3bdecf4c] Installing the skill
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker reached with value 9000
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker reached with value 10000
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: Requesting shuttle move to...
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: On Ticker Behaviour ended...
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded] Assembly: Move request for shuttle
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-21b66b55-7185-463c-b7df-63997085f1c5] The Module with name TakeoutPlace is active now!
[INFORMATION, 8:37:45pm, AGENT-5dd23157-e134-4ead-9568-09357b1267a7] Maintainer: Received: Request for shuttle move from Address [
    type = "Address"
    participantId = 69b2889f-2a15-46a5-86d5-12922b60fdded
    spaceId = SpaceID [
        type = "SpaceID"
        id = 2c38fb7f-f363-4f6e-877b-110b1f07cc77
        contextID = 2c38fb7f-f363-4f6e-877b-110b1f07cc77
        spaceSpec = interface io.sarl.core.OpenEventSpaceSpecification
    ]
]
    
```

Figure 27: Interaction Example of communication between and inside Janus agents ⁷

⁶ SARL IDE (Event-Trigger inside of agents)

⁷ SARL IDE (Console-Log as interaction example for agent communication)

After spawning the related agents, their initial behavior is started and related skills, for example for assembly, are initialized. The request for transport can be performed from a resource agent, for example from the assembly agent, towards the transport agent.

Agents can be modelled by using capacities with skills [8]. The resource agent for the “Storage and Assembly” production module consists of an assembly behavior that implements an assembly skill and a skill for pick and place to get the product from the shuttle transporter inside the module. The precondition which must be met, before the skill is executed, is to call the transport, resulting in an own behavior trigger inside the agent.

Figure 28: Agent behavior and skill implementation in Janus with SARL ⁸

The implementation of a skill can be done inside an agent object and be used inside a behavior [11], to execute several commands of this skill in a sequenced manner. For example, the execution of the assembly skill with the shuttle system to get the workpiece carrier for the product must always follow a predefined process. In Figure 29, the assembly skill of the resource agent for the assembly production module is presented.

⁸ SARL IDE (SARL Objects for agent behavior and skills)

```

/*
 * Starting the process and build the command properties.
 */

json = BuildJSONCommand(agentname)

/*
 * Initiate lock of production asset occupation state machine
 */

Lock(json)

/*
 * Initiate Inward
 */

Inward(skillparam, json)

/*
 * Initiate Assembly
 */

Assembly(json)

/*
 * Initiate Outward
 */

Outward(skillparam, json)

/*
 * Initiate free of production asset occupation state machine
 */

Free(json)

wake(new Skill_End)

```

Figure 29: Implemented assembly skill functions inside of assembly behavior of a Janus agent ⁹

It is possible to submit several parametrizations for the call of the related skills. Furthermore, for agents which interact with assets that are represented with an AAS, it is necessary to build up command messages, for example in JSON, which are sent to the AAS methods as parameters. The commands are executed towards the assets AAS by using the JSON, which can be prepared individually. The communication pattern inside the skill is customizable and changeable, so it is possible to keep a predefined skill sequence inside of an agent’s behavior and to change the skill implementation with a modified or a completely new object, without changing the basic agent communication or behavior pattern in the source code in a general way. This allows individual development and customization, without many changes of basic objects like agents or behaviors. The AAS communication inside the skill objects is furthermore part of the MAS4AI framework interface setup, as well as the integration of semantic requests, using an RDF-Store.

⁹ SARM IDE (Skill usage inside of agent behavior)

4.4 Execution and validation with the whole MAS4AI system

Related to the Smart Factory use case, the MAS4AI framework focused in the current state on the integration between the MAS component and the AAS / Data component, which has been built on implementations with the BaSyx-Middleware.

The main concept for interaction of the MAS component with other elements of the MAS4AI framework can be seen in the concept of changeable capacities and skills, following the concept in the Janus framework. The definition of capacities allows an abstract method definition, that can be implemented from various skills in a different way. This allows the definition of software patterns, which can be implemented from agents, without predefinition of the implementation itself, which is integrated very often in an individual manner.

This concept can also be used for the integration with other MAS4AI components, like RDF-Store or the integration of external message channels with Apache Kafka. This allows the setup of various agent templates with a predefined behavior but encapsulates the concrete technology-related interface implementation inside the skill. This approach enables a flexible setup and possibilities for Use Case-specific customization in the MAS component of the MAS4AI framework and can also be realized in other frameworks if this software pattern can be implemented there. Another usage of this pattern can be evaluated in the Jade Framework, by using the standard Java interface pattern, which build the basis of the Janus capacity [12], but without domain-specific skill setup within agents.

```
capacity AssemblyCapacity {
    /* Build JSON Argument Call String */
    def BuildJSONCommand(asset : String) : String
    /* Get Control-Lock of Production Asset State Machine */
    def Lock(json : String) : Integer
    /* Invoke Assembly */
    def Assembly(json : String) : Integer
    /* Remove Control-Lock of Production Asset State Machine */
    def Free(json : String) : Integer
}
```

Figure 30: Assembly capacity in SARL ¹⁰

¹⁰ SARL IDE (Capacity Example)

Inside of a skill, the given capacity can be extended with a corresponding implementation. The skill can request the AAS registry of the BaSyx-Middleware to get the related asset and to connect to the AAS submodel, processing a prebuild JSON-command to AAS methods.

```

override Assembly(json : String) : Integer {

    /*
     * AAS-Example-Command
     */

    var url_command : String = "" // Insert AAS-URL here
    var response : int

    if (url_command.equals("")) {
        info("Access of AAS-Function Assembly - TBD.")
        return response
    }

    var url : URL = new URL(url_command)
    var connection : HttpURLConnection = url.openConnection() as HttpURLConnection

    connection.setDoOutput(true)
    connection.setInstanceFollowRedirects(false)

    connection.setRequestMethod("POST")
    connection.setRequestProperty("Content-Type", "application/json")

    connection.getOutputStream().write(json.getBytes("UTF-8"))

    response = connection.getResponseCode()
    info("Response code for Assemble is: " + response)

    connection.disconnect();

    return response
}

```

Figure 31: Assembly Skill in SARL ¹¹

The communication related part of the MAS framework thus can be built of reusable communication patterns for several protocols, for example to interact with a AAS with a REST-interface or directly by using OPC UA. For further integration of an RDF-Store or Apache Kafka, it is also possible to provide suitable connectors inside a skill.

¹¹ SARL IDE (Implemented Skill Example)

4.5 Summarized results

For the prototypical implementation of the Smart Factory testbed environment with the PL4 line and the MAS4AI framework evaluation, the methodical approach for the iterative development provided the possibility to reach the defined development goals of each iteration. Thereby, the system setup and evaluation of the overall framework setup, consisting of MAS4AI framework components like the MAS-System itself, as well as the AAS / Data layer as representation of the manufacturing environment could be enhanced with new functionalities.

The status of implemented agent types in the testbed environment, related to the described requirements, are presented in Table 16.

Agent	Input	Output	Status
Production module agent	Raw material	Processed material	Successful integration
Transport agent	Transported good	Transported good	Successful integration
Quality Inspection agent	Product	Product (+Quality assessment)	In Progress (AAS prepared)
Energy agent	Energy	-	In Progress (AAS prepared)

Table 16: Status of integrated agents in the testbed environment (1st iteration)

The preparation of AAS with uniform interfaces to interact with the manufacturing environment has been evaluated as essential for integration and communication with the MAS component of the proposed MAS4AI framework. The interaction itself has been successfully evaluated with AAS and Registry, which is built with the BaSyx-Middleware and hosted with REST-Interface. A point which is very important for future integration is an event-based subscription mechanism if agents execute tasks of assets, because of the asynchronous execution by using the AAS it would be necessary to iterative load the AAS with its properties to get information about successful or failure during the execution. Therefore, topics of Apache Kafka or MQTT could be used.

Another important point of the current evaluation is the usability of agent patterns in the MAS component for several agent types. The resource agent type has been adapted for several agents of production modules as well as for the transportation asset. The holonic agent controls the lifecycle of all related agent types. The skill approach enables the possibility of an abstract integration in agent types and behaviors and is exchangeable, for example to support a communication with an AAS with REST. The integration of AAS for holonic agents and their agent types will be integrated as well as skills for communication with the RDF-Store, the integration of message channel systems like Apache Kafka and HMI-Devices.

5 Conclusion of first iteration

The implementation of the MAS4AI prototype has shown, that the asset representation as AAS is essential for MAS connection and interaction. The possibility to get data from assets and to interact with them with predefined interfaces, enables a better integration for MAS-Systems. Furthermore, the prototype showed, that the execution of a production flow with components of the MAS4AI framework is possible. The iterative development method thus makes it possible to build up the framework in a modular way and to enhance functionalities.

Figure 32: Upcoming iteration built of Smart Factory MAS4AI prototype

The upcoming development iterations will focus more on a distributed deployment of MAS4AI components, by using Docker technology for each component. Therefore, predefined interfaces with API can help to build up single components in a way, that they are independent of the used solution, for example if another technology should be used than the BaSyx-Middleware. In the next steps, the messaging system component and the knowledge base should be integrated and the setup of the already used components more developed in terms of customizable patterns. Furthermore, the integration of OPC UA in skills for direct AAS communication from agents will be considered. The integration and evaluation of more agent types, as described in the use case requirements, are also focused for upcoming prototyping. The integration and usage of AI agents, for example for planning or machine learning, into the shown prototypical implemented MAS4AI framework is also planned for upcoming development iterations.

6 Scope of Smart Factory 2nd testbed evaluation

6.1 Shared Production testbed use cases

The SmartFactory-KL production environment is established as prototypical vision for Shared Production, which follows the approach of a modular, flexible production system, that consists of a skill-based approach for modular production units, sustainable aspects and autonomous concepts like distributed agent-based control and the vision of Production Level 4, where the Human is supported due to level 4 of autonomy [13].

Figure 33: Shared Production approach of SmartFactory-KL [13]

The SmartFactory-KL Shared Production consist of several demonstrator testbeds, in which the Production Level 4 (PL4) demonstrator as Production-Island “Java” of the DFKI has been developed and build up as modular skill-based factory testbed for modern automation hardware and software.

The concept of modular production units with distributed setup and agent-based control has been extended and applied to further CPPS of the SmartFactory-KL testbeds, like the Production-Island “Kuba”, which also consist of several skill-based CPPM which are interconnected with a transportation system. The modules of this demonstrator are also modular as well, so that they can consist of several submodules, which can be combined individually to fulfill the product requirements. In Figure 34 the Production-Island “Kuba” is shown.

The Production-Island “Java” (PL4-Demonstrator) was primarily used in the first prototypical iteration of the MAS4AI SmartFactory-KL testbed evaluation. The Production-Island “Kuba” and the related modular modules with submodels are used additionally for several enhancements and experiments in the second prototypical iteration of the MAS4AI SmartFactory-KL testbed evaluation.

Figure 34: SmartFactory - Production-Island "Kuba"

The product inside of the Shared Production network consist of various parts, which are manufactured across the Production-Islands. The final product is a nubstone truck which can be manufactured in various combinations. The truck consists of a semitrailer-truck and a semitrailer, which can furthermore consist of various individualizable product components across the Shared Production Network, as shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35: SmartFactory product for Shared Production

The in the 2nd iteration used hardware-related components, which are not related to the Cyber-Physical Production Modules, assets are listed in Table 17.

Type	Name	Manufacturer
Edge Cloud Server	OneCite	GEC / Rittal
Conveyor system of Demonstrator „Java“	TracSet	Montratec
Conveyor system of Demonstrator „Kuba“	ACOPOStrak	B&R
Tablet	Ipad	Apple
Smart Glasses	Hololens 2	Microsoft
Infrastructure Nodes	Infrastrukturknoten	SmartFactory
ATV	Robotino	Festo
Manual assembly station	HAP	SmartFactory

Table 17: Hardware-related components and assets (2nd Iteration)

6.2 SmartFactory Software Basis

The SmartFactory software basis of the testbeds consists of several components which are used in the use cases. The components of the Production-Island “Java” (PL4-Demonstrator), which were the starting point for the first prototypical implementations and integrations for the MAS4AI deliverable and described as results of the first iteration, about the initially considered structure in Figure 9.

The initial considered architecture for the MAS4AI prototype was mainly divided in several layers, considering various aspects and concepts of the related testbed. On the Edge-Layer, the Cyber-Physical Production Modules are considered, where production capabilities, e.g., Pick and Place, are encapsulated with the skill-based approach and provided with the protocol OPC UA. The Production Flow Control Unit, which works as central coordinator for the production process, was replaced with the first MAS4AI prototype for the PL4-demonstrator.

Related to the Integration-Layer, components are used mainly as Registry for Services as well for Production Modules, as well as Discovery to search for respective Services and Production Skills. Furthermore, on this level, the trusted Cloud Connector, which is used for example for interconnection in terms of a Shared Production interconnection is located.

On the Plant-Layer, software components for the control of products, process and resources are considered. For manufacturing of individualized products, an own component for product design and configuration is considered, as well as the product management in terms of a digital object memory. The Production Flow Control, which is considered for handling the production process, and communication with Production Modules on the resource level thus fulfills the requirements to manufacture the purchased products. This component was then replaced with the distributed holonic structured agents of the first MAS4AI prototype.

The updated components and related protocols of the SmartFactory-KL testbed at the beginning of the second iteration of prototyping are described in Table 18.

Protocol	Architecture Component
OPC UA	Production Modules Production Flow Control HMI MAS4AI Agent System Prototype
MQTT	Cloud Applications Enterprise Resource Planning System Asset Administration Shell (Dimofac)
REST	Enterprise Resource Planning System Production Flow Control Production Design Production Configuration Registry (Skills and Topology) API Management Discovery MAS4AI Agent System Planning and ML-Algorithms Quality Services
Profibus	Production Modules Infrastructure Nodes
FTP	Data Exchange, for example for Quality Control pictures

Table 18: SmartFactory architecture components and protocols (2nd iteration)

The services with security mechanisms are presented in Table 19.

Cloud Services	Comm.-Protocol	Security
IBM Cloud	IBM PSB	Authentication
Gaia X Connector	MQTT & IDS (HTTP)	Authentication (Certificates)
IDS Connector	REST	Authentication (Certificates/ID)

Table 19: Clouds and connectors (2nd iteration)

6.3 Requirements Scope of second prototype

Based on the results of the first prototypical MAS4AI implementation, considering the SmartFactory-KL production environment with related assets and their software basis, Asset Administration Shells as well as preparations for Digital Twins, CPPM and software components could be considered as I4.0-Component. The role of the AAS thus has been extended, not only representing a hardware-involved component-structure but rather considering the respective software elements as well and the usage for the MAS as well. The AAS has been evaluated by using the BaSyx-Middleware and OPC UA. The integration in the Dimofac-Platform is thus of interest for further usage, focusing the interoperability of the whole MAS4AI approach. For the second iteration of the MAS4AI approach inside of SmartFactory-KL, the enhancement of the AAS-Layer for physical and virtual components with several technologies and implementation should be used as enabler for flexible integration possibilities. The higher degree of modularized demonstrator-components, for example modular modules with submodels, one requirement is furthermore the necessity for the consideration of the holonic approach on the respective agent level. This provides a more detailed possibility to reach for the requirements of the holonic structured system approach.

The first iteration of results from the SmartFactory-KL testbed provided the idea of several agent types, which can be used for industrial application, which were used and further developed in the second iteration as well for other pilot cases as templates and this in a more generalized way so far. Nevertheless, further agent types from the first iteration provided requirements, which are topic for a special consideration in the second iteration. These agent types inherit the integration of specified and prototypically implemented planning and machine learning agents as AI agents, as result from the projects Work Packages 4 and 5.

The requirement for the second MAS4AI prototype of the SmartFactory-KL is to demonstrate the integration possibilities of agents based on the existence of defined interfaces, regardless of providing an AAS for the algorithm or the requirement of a more encapsulated integration. Furthermore, the specification of further agent types which are not part in other industrial pilot cases, for example energy agents which can provide wide-range functionality, is considered. The specification of energy agents thus also provides a full example for interaction with other agent types (planning as well resource agents) and various behavior which can also be intended as own agents as planned in the first iteration, like data collection, storage, and usage for different necessities like monitoring, planning as transparency. Additionally, the prototypical realization of a general designed AMS agent for the MAS4AI framework as well as approaches for HMI agents are demonstrated.

For the second iteration of MAS4A, the system setup and requirements of the first iteration should be considered as basis and extended for the related agent types. For this, the list of the foreseen agents of the first iteration is considered, which should be implemented and evaluated, as presented in Table 20. This list was created on the requirements of needed agent types, based on collected requirements in WP1 and which were considered in the first and second iteration of the SmartFactory-KL testbed. The results of the second iteration furthermore focus on the integration of ML and Planning agents, of AMS and HMI agents and Energy Agents on resource level. Due to the highly individualized agent types which are pilot line specific implemented in MAS4AI, for example agents for Safety or Product purpose.

Agent	Type	Considered in 2 nd Iteration
Local planning agent	Production planning	x
Resource agent	Resource	(Part of 1 st Iteration)
Production module agent	Resource	(Part of 1 st Iteration)
Transport agent	Resource	(Part of 1 st Iteration)
Quality inspection agent	Quality inspection	x
Safety agent	Safety	Not considered
AMS/HMI agent	HMI	x
Energy agent	Resource	x
Infrastructure agent	Information	(As Behavior of Energy agents)
Data collection agent	Information	(As Behavior of Energy agents)
Product agent	Product	Not considered

Table 20: SmartFactory: overview of expected agents and their types (2nd iteration)

Related to several domains of the use case requirement analysis, the following scope has been defined for the Smart Factory use case, and the requirements of the first iteration are enhanced and extended towards the second iteration.

Agent name	Description	Domain
Local planning agent	The local planning agent can perform job-shop scheduling with a limited number of machines and interaction with a global planning service.	Time, Flexibility
Quality Inspection agent	The quality inspection agent able to perform a classification of products based on defects and a classification of defective products based on the possibility of repair.	Sustainability, Quality

HMI agent	The HMI agent is an agent with interfaces to data visualization and database services.	Human Machine Interaction
Energy agent	The energy agent fulfills the requirement to create transparency about the energy data behavior of production assets as well as for the usage of the data, like planning purpose.	Energy, Sustainability

Table 21: Categorization of agents (2nd iteration)

Furthermore, transport agents have specific requirements, following aspects of safety, reliability, energy management that have impact to their communication and information. A list of expected physical interactions between agents and the process environment is also presented in Table 22. For the proposed prototype development and evaluation, the implementation of production module agents as well as transport agents are mainly in focus of the setup.

Agent	Input	Output
Production module agent	Raw material	Processed material
Transport agent	Transported good	Transported good
Quality Inspection agent	Product	Product (+Quality assessment)
Energy agent	Energy	Energy data and usage

Table 22: SmartFactory: expected physical interactions between agents and their environment (2nd iteration)

The list of special considerations for agents related with specific context regarding ethics or trustworthiness are presented. Due to the focus of the first and second iterations prototype, the following aspects are not mainly focused. For the applied data collection in the second iteration, only energy-related data was considered. The HMI-concept and AMS-GUI thus focus on a general conceptual approach in the context of this deliverable.

Agent	Special Considerations
Safety agent	Safety regulations
HMI agent	Trustworthiness, Usability / accessibility
Data collection agent	Ethics (privacy rights, legal...)
Product agent	Reliability, Privacy, Trustworthiness

Table 23: SmartFactory: special considerations (2nd iteration)

Predefined agent communication, which is based on the identified agent types, is necessary to setup the main interactions between several agent types with events and the related message. The considered agents for SmartFactory-KL, as it is expected to meet the requirements of the

second iteration, together with the corresponding links between agents that are expected to interact within the process, is presented in Table 24.

Local planning agent	Task scheduling data. Process-related time to fulfil production orders. Energy data for multi-criterial optimization. Other data needs to be assessed during the MAS4AI project.
Quality Inspection agent	Picture and configuration criteria for batch size 1 quality control. “Ground truth” Data of the correct product configuration.
Production Module Agent	Sensor and Actor Data of the corresponding Modules in OPC UA – with properties and operations (as skill-based approach) Each current module states Skill-related time and energy data and their sequences Data about current configuration Energy Consumption
HMI Agent	Status of the production orders Status of the production modules Machine data Database containing component documentation Information about the current operator
AMS and configuration Agent	Agent type patterns (based on Janus Framework) Agents Registry and Discovery Service Asset Administration Shell (Submodel for Asset Interface Description) Agent Lifecycle services and information (for instantiated agents)

Table 24: Required Agent data (2nd iteration)

The interactions of each agent types, following the given overall setup, is also listed in Table 25.

Agent	Interaction mechanisms
Local planning agent	Local planning agents: Planned schedule Product agents: type, processing step, location, deadlines Production module agents: Skills, availability, key processing indicators Quality inspection agents: Defect products Energy agents: Energy prices, adjust machine performance Infrastructure agents
Resource agent (incl. Production Module agent, Transport agent, Quality inspection)	HMI agent (to interact with humans) Safety agent (safety assessment, human interaction) Energy agent (collect energy needs, (optional) adjust performance, (optional) alter state (standby, offline, etc.)) Data collection (collects data from resource agent)
Safety agent	HMI agent (show safety level, safety information, interaction with / location of operators) Data collection agent (sensors/actors, create protocols)
Energy agent	Product agent (fill lifecycle file) Data collection agent (report energy consumption)

Table 25: SmartFactory: interactions between agents and associated requirements (2nd iteration)

6.4 Method for Prototype Development

The Smart Factory prototype development and evaluation for the MAS4AI framework in the second iterations subsequent follows an iterative software prototyping approach of the first prototypical implementation, with goal of validation of the WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 results of the given project. The setup of the second MAS prototype, which is based on a MAS framework in combination with a message-based middleware solution, like Apache Kafka and BaSyx, is thus enhanced with the integration of Dimofac-Platform AAS and considering industrial Internet-of-Thing's web service technologies like HTTP and MQTT as well as possibilities for configuration and parametrization.

The prototyping continues to follow the aspects of the first iteration prototype and considers this method for development and prototype evaluation with further testbed setups:

- e. Digital twin preparation and integration with the AI agents for early assessment,
- f. pilot setup that involves integration of existing legacy systems,
- g. execution and validation of the individual agents and
- h. execution and validation with the whole MAS4AI system

With the preparation of digital twins and AAS for hardware-related components as well as for software related components, the integration into the MAS4AI framework will be proceeded in the same manner. The AAS integration for the Dimofac-Platform will enhance the possibilities of hardware-related assets and the usage of AAS for algorithms will thus focus on the main integration aspects of AI agents.

The infrastructure components of the first prototypical MAS4AI results of the SmartFactory-KL could be used in the same manner, like Registry and Discovery Services, and be applied in the same manner to other demonstrators, to evaluate the method in another constellation.

Individual agents which are considered in the MAS4AI requirements analysis and not be part of the first iteration results are considered in the second prototype, like AI agents for planning and machine learning, as well as for energy behavior of production environments.

The implementation of the agents and the evaluation with the whole MAS4AI framework also considers the results of the work packages of the MAS4AI project and focus on the aspects that are not part of the first evaluation. The iterative integration and implementation thus continuous for these components in the second prototypical results.

7 Smart Factory MAS4AI 2nd Implementation

The Smart Factory testbed implementation of the MAS4AI framework follows the proposed setup and content of the work packages. The structure is presented in Figure 36.

Figure 36: MAS4AI-Framework

The MAS4AI framework is realized in the SmartFactory-KL testbed and thus is focused on prototypical implementation of components and setups of the framework integration. As focus on the implementation in this document, following main aspects and considered:

- Ongoing MAS4AI Framework setup
 - Creation and Usage of Information Models for assets and agents
 - Configuration and Execution Service with Registry and UI
 - MAS Runtime environment (realized in Janus SARL)
 - AI algorithms for integration in related Agents for Planning or ML purpose
- Application of the first developed MAS4AI-MVP on further production testbeds, like the KUBA production island
- Further application of the holonic structured MAS-architecture for modular production systems, as well for its subsystems, which is demonstrated on modular modules
- Prototypical specification and integration of new Agent Types like Energy-Agents, Planning Agents as well as ML-Agents for Quality Services

7.1 Distributed Holonic Implementation

The implementation from the first MAS4AI testbed evaluation focused a holonic approach for distributed and multi-layer agent-system control. The approach has been developed and applied from the conceptual design to further testbeds of the SmartFactory-KL. The Production-Island Kuba also considers the basic elements of the MAS4AI framework, and thus the holonic structure, where the handling of this Cyber-Physical Production System is represented as own holonic structured resource agent, which consist of inherited resource agents for the control of its respective production modules directly with OPC UA. The overall setup is presented in Figure 37.

Figure 37: Distributed Agent Setup on Kuba Production Island

The testbed demonstrator furthermore consists of the possibility to integrate the concept of a modular module, exemplarily realized by using related submodules on the next level, in which an own holonic structured resource agent is used, with the task to coordinate the related submodules for assembly tasks. The Shared Production network of the SmartFactory-KL thus manifests the distributed holonic implementation approach across the several demonstrators, as well as in the demonstrator-setup itself. The communication between the related holonic structured agents is enabled by using the concept of the Asset Administration Shell, considering the agents in a similar manner as the related assets, as well as Apache Kafka as commonly used communication channel. To interact with a Shared Production environment, the usage of further communication channels, like an IDS-Connector as well as a Gaia-X-Connectors could be used similar, integrating them in the Janus agent as communication skill.

7.2 Dimofac Platform-Integration

The integration of MAS4AI framework with Dimofac Digital Platform was done prototypically in scope of the activities in the task T2.2 of the WP2. The structure of the prototype is shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38: Agent Management System Dimofac Prototype

It consists of the following main components:

- The Dimofac-Platform for hosting the AASs of all the agents and agent types of the MAS4AI system
- The platform is delivered in the docker container and has all the required components to be deployed with the minimum setup.
- The Dimofac-Platform also provides the MQTT-broker, which is used as a messaging middleware to integrate Janus runtime and the Dimofac server.
- MQTT is use as a message-based communication middleware between the Agents and their AASs.

The prototype partially implements the use-case of activating an agent, which was described in the deliverable of Task 2.2. The prototype thus can be use by the developers and integrators as a bootstrap example for developing the solutions based on the MAS4AI and the Dimofac-Platform.

Figure 39: Integration between the MAS4AI and the Dimofac

Figure 39 shows the integration of the AMS agent with its AAS, which is hosted on the Dimofac Digital Platform. As a prerequisite to the use-case all the to-be deployed agents should exist in the SARL IDE as the agents’ classes. Their AASs should be created in one of the AAS modeling tools, e.g., AASX-explorer. To upload the newly created AAS to the Dimofac it is necessary to start the web server from the AASX-explorer and use the REST API provided by the Dimofac-Platform to upload the AAS to the platform (Step 1 on the Figure 39). For configuring the communication publish-subscribe channels of the Dimofac-Platform a special configuration file is used. In the example two operations were configured, so that the Dimofac system publish the defined message to the configured topics. The agents use the information from the predefined “assetInterfaceDescriptor” submodel, to automatically configure themselves for listening and publishing to the MQTT topics. Each agent has a skill that specializes the “agent_aas_interpreter” capacity in Janus, which is used for the parsing and interpretation of the standard MAS4AI submodels. Several skills can implement the same capacity. This enables the agent to work with different AAS hosting platforms. When an agent is activated, it gets the information regarding MQTT communication using REST API (Step 3 on Figure 39) and set its MQTT skill to interact with the Dimofac server. Now, when a user call an operation on the submodel, the message will be received by the agent’s skill and the event will be generated, so the agent can react on it (Step 4 on Figure 39).

7.3 Agent Management System Prototype

For the Agent Management System (AMS) agent in the SmartFactory-KL, two prototypical implementations are proposed, one on basis of the BaSyx-Middleware, and the second on basis of the Dimofac-Platform.

The BaSyx-Prototype consists of four components of the MAS4AI framework, which are also considered in Figure 40:

- BaSyx-Middleware for hosting the AAS for the AMS, providing configuration possibilities
- Janus SARL MAS for the related agents
- Apache Kafka as communication channel between the AMS and the related AAS
- Docker for deployment of spawned agents

Figure 40: BaSyx Prototype of the Agent Management System

The prototypical implementation in BaSyx provides the AAS and Submodels, as well as the possibility of a Registry and Discovery. Agents and their related AAS of the MAS4AI framework, which are both hosted as own Docker containers are provided in the system. By using the AAS of the AMS, it is possible to access the lifecycle functionalities of those agents and thus to spawn or delete agents in the system. The AMS agent itself, which is based on the Janus SARL Framework is configured by the hosted AAS and subscribes to the same broker and required topics. The common communication channel is Apache Kafka.

The service frontend thus consists of a Micro Frontend concept, as shown in Figure 41, thus consist of the Frontend, the API-Layer, and the Agents with their services.

Figure 41: Frontend Concept of AMS Agents

The UI thus displays information which is based on the configured AMS as well on the lifecycle and configuration information for each agent type in the system which is hosted in AAS of the BaSyx-Middleware. Figure 42 shows the approach for the UI-Prototype, which enables the management of MAS4AI agent types in the AMS.

Figure 42: UI-Prototype for AMS, based on AAS-Backend Information

7.4 HMI-Agent conceptual approach

Related to the integration of Human Smart Workers into the MAS4AI framework, a first conceptual approach has been developed. The core concept is based on the integration of a Human Smart Worker as part of a shared assembly task on the Production-Island “Kuba”. The gripper, that can provide and thus combine product parts, and a human worker can collaborate on an agent-level. The related information is thus stored in the AAS of the gripper component agent in form as resource agent as well as in the HMI-Agent which acts as operator in the MAS4AI system. The collaboration approach with relation to the MAS4AI elements is shown in Figure 43.

Figure 43: HMI-Agent conceptual approach for a MAS4AI

The visualization and UI-Design could thus follow the approach of the AMS-Agent UI-Design, which is also based on the AAS-Backend information. The communication of an HMI agent as well as the consideration of agent behavior must follow about the special considerations as described in Table 23.

7.5 Energy-Agents

In the SmartFactory use case, the infrastructure-related setup is modular as well, providing the possibility to supply modular production modules with energy, network connectivity for data acquisition and monitoring [14]. The realization of this concept manifests in the approach of the Infrastructure Node, which provides connections for four production modules and comes with metering hardware to control and observe energy-related data.

Figure 44: Infrastructure Node (Picture by A. Sell) [14]

The hardware and software settings of the Infrastructure Node, which is used for the “Java” and “Kuba”-Demonstrator, consist of following components, which are described in Table 26:

Hardware / Software	Description	Usage
Bosch Rexroth IPC (Soft PLC)	IPC for data processing and OPC UA interface host	Data processing from Modbus / Profinet
Weidmüller Energy Meter D370	Component for energy measurements	Integrated 4x, one for each module connection
Weidmüller Software for Energy Meter	Software Library for D370 Energy Meter	Provision of energy data in Modbus protocol
OPC UA Adapter as Energy Interface	OPC UA Interface for Modbus Values	Translation of Modbus Values in OPC UA properties
OPC UA Energy AAS	OPC UA Adapter as AAS	OPC UA Information Model based on AAS and Energy Companion Specifications

Table 26: Infrastructure Node Components

The proposed values, which are thus considered in the OPC UA Adapter and provided in the interface are presented in Table 27:

Properties (provided for all 3 phases)	SI Unit
Voltage	V
Current	A
Active Power	W
Reactive Power	VAR
Aparent Power	VA
Cos	Phi

Table 27: Considered properties of the OPC UA energy-interface

The Asset Administration Shell is thus realized in OPC UA, as presented in Figure 45, as well as the data collector component in the BaSyx-Middleware, which is used the structured to collect data and to store it in database.

Figure 45: Energy Consumption Interface of an Infrastructure Node

The constellation to measure, collect and store energy data in modular skill-based production environments with the BaSyx-Middleware on this basis, was proposed in [15]. The measurement of energy from modular production units can thus be used to create and observe energy profiles on a more detailed level, as shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46: Skill-based load profile of a Pick and Place Skill of the PL4-Demonstrator

The setup of the Production-Island “Kuba” of the SmartFactory-KL is also based on the energy provision with an own Infrastructure Node. The connections of this Infrastructure Node support the production modules of an Assembly Module (5G-Module), a Quality Check-Module, the Transport System “Acopotrak” and thus a modular module with submodules, with a Gripper-Component and submodules for 3-Printing and manual assembly station, as shown in Figure 47.

Figure 47: Energy-System of Production Island Kuba

The distributed production setup of the Production-Island “Kuba” provides the possibility to specify energy agents for data collection, based on predefined energy AAS of an Infrastructure Node. The usage of energy agents thus can provide encapsulated functionalities to access the AAS of a production module, which is thus handled and controlled by resource agents. An energy agent communicated with the resource agent if a respective production skill is executed and decides to collect data from the assets AAS to build up specific load profiles as well as to use the collected data for monitoring purposes.

Figure 48: Integration of Energy Agents

An energy agent could be located on the resource agent-level, interacting with the resource agents of a given context of a production system. The energy agent thus could also be part of an holonic structured resource agent, like it is provided in the modular production module of the Production-Island “Kuba”. Following the holonic approach, an energy agent thus can be structured in a holonic way. The communication considers the beginning of the executing of production skills as well state machine statuses of the assets from the resource agent.

The collected data could be used to record energy profiles for individual combined production environments inside of a resource holon as well for new skills, which should be executed. The stored data can thus be used as knowledge base for energy agents, using the BaSyx-Middleware or Apache Kafka as Data Lakes and thus to provide subsequent agent behavior, like monitoring of the energy parameters during production and for energy consumption prediction, if the data

is combined with planning data. Therefore, the interaction to production plan data is required and part of the agent interaction and communication. The content of the communication between resource agents as well as planning agents can be based on the I4.0-Language. The setup of this combined integration can be seen in Figure 49, considering several agent types, their skills, and the usage of data in terms of data collection and infrastructure usage. The energy agent thus also provides an example on how the necessity of data collection and infrastructure agents as requirement for the second iteration prototyping could also be integrated directly as behavior.

Figure 49: Energy Agents for skill-based energy profiling and usage, extending the approach of [15]

The energy agent encapsulates the logic in an own Janus Behavior as well the interfaces to interact with the database or to access the energy information model of OPC UA with own Janus Capacities and Skills.

The energy data thus provides the possibility to further use it for predictions of energy consumptions if the data is combined with scheduling data. Furthermore, the product-related energy part could be used for related products of the Shared Production Use Case if they provide a Digital Lifecycle Passport to consider energy data for creation and processing of product parts with relation to the Bill of Materials.

7.6 Planning Agent Integration with RL-Algorithm

To schedule the different tasks onto machines we integrated a Planning Agent in the second prototypical implementation phase. The Planning Agent is an online scheduling approach, i.e., instead of assigning the task to a machine at a specific point in time in advance the task will be assigned to the machines during production dynamically. The procedure contains three parts:

- The Resource Agent collects the state observations and queries the RL service.
- The RL service computes a bid from the state observations of the Resource Agent.
- The Planning Agent collects and compares the bids from the Resource Agents and assigns the task to one Resource Agent.

Figure 50 shows the involved components. The Resource Agents implements the provided interface of the external RL Service. Beyond that they are spawned in the inner context of the Planning Agent, i.e., the Resource Agents are part of the larger Planning Agent Holon. While the bidding protocol is implemented in Janus, the bid itself is computed in an external Python service. This service is integrated as a docker multi-container application over REST into the Janus framework. The bid computation is integrated into the Janus framework as skill of the Resource Agent. The comparison of the bids is again implemented as Janus skill within the Planning Agent.

Figure 50: Component diagram showing the integration of the RL-service into the multi-agent system

The overall scheduling process is illustrated as a communication diagram in Figure 51 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** The Planning Agent initiates the next scheduling process. He asks all Resource Agents living in his holon for a bid regarding a job. Hence, the number of requested Resource Agents depends on the plant setup. For reasons of clarity, we only

used three Resource Agents exemplary in Figure 51. Since the resources in the factory are managed via the Janus framework, the scheduling algorithm itself does not need to change if the plant setup changes. The Resource Agents check whether they can process the job. If they do not have the correct skill for the job, they respond to the Planning Agent with “Deny”. If they can process the job, they collect all relevant observations and request the RL service. The RL service returns a bid., which the Resource Agent then forwards to the Planning Agent. The Planning Agent validates the bidding results, determines the agent with the highest bid and assigns the job to it. The whole sequence is executed during production repetitively. In this way a schedule for the production is created.

Figure 51: Communication flow during online scheduling

7.7 QS-Agent Integration with ML-Algorithm

In the SmartFactory-KL the QS-Agent is used to handle cameras for product quality checks. The Quality Agent was thus part of the first prototypical iteration, which acts in the form of a resource agent to control the production skill-related capability to make pictures and process it by using a neuronal trained network. The machine learning service thus was provided as two separate skills of the asset to make and upload a picture, as well to use the picture as input for the machine learning service for object detection and thus for the quality check. Related to the PL4-Demonstrator environment, the first quality check is performed after the assembly of the product and the second quality check is performed before its final delivery. Thus, the image is taken when the product is in front of the module.

Figure 52: SmartFactory PL4 demonstrator with two quality modules marked in red

The machine learning service to proceed the Quality Checks for the Production-Island “Java” based on the PL4-Demonstrator as well for the Productions-Island “Kuba” is trained with related training data on basis of a neural network, using TensorFlow object detection API is used to train the model. The setup is presented in Figure 52. If a picture is taken in the demonstrator, it is sent to the service to classify the objects on the image and to compare it against the products specification.

An example of the product of the PL4-Demonstrator of the SmartFactory-KL with different recognized elements is shown in Figure 53.

Figure 53: SmartFactory-KL product (USB pen drive) with classified results of image recognition

The encapsulated Quality Check-Skill was realized in the first iteration prototype with an OPC UA Skill Model. The Quality Agent behavior thus has been extended in the second iteration of the prototypical implementation, to also consider a behavior to directly connect to the camera of the respective Quality Check Module by using a webservice as well to process the result (image in binary code) to the machine learning service.

The logic and interface communication are therefore structured as own Janus Skill in the Quality Check Agent, as proposed in Figure 54. The agent is thus communicating by using the REST-Interface of the camera and the machine learning service. The parametrization of the REST-Calls is thus encapsulated as Janus Skills.

Figure 54: Integration of the Quality Check Capacity of Janus Agents

The Janus SARL related implementation provides an example, on how external services for machine learning could be integrated in general. Regarding to the integration approach of Work Package 5, the agent skills could be designed with Janus Capacities in an abstract way and be implemented in a concrete manner with a Janus Skill. The Janus Capacity and Skill-Interaction thus enables the possibility to interact with individual interfaces as well as with the AAS.

Figure 55 shows the example for the Janus Capacity as pattern to interact with the camera for data collection as well to call the quality check service.


```

12
13 capacity QualityAlgorithmCapacity {
14
15     /* Build JSON command for input data collection */
16
17     def BuildJSONCommandForInputData(inputParameter : String) : String
18
19     /* Access data source with JSON parameter to collect data */
20
21     def DataCollection(dataSourceAddress : String, json : String) : String
22
23     /* Build JSON command for algorithm access */
24
25     def BuildJSONCommandForAlgorithm(dataCollection : String) : String
26
27     /* Access algorithm with JSON parameter data */
28
29     def QualityAlgorithm(algorithmAddress : String, json : String) : String
30
31 }
32
    
```

Figure 55: Janus Capacity for Quality Check Machine Learning Service ¹²

Figure 56 shows the example for the implemented Janus Skill.


```

49
50 /* Access data source with JSON parameter to collect data
51 */
52
53 override DataCollection(dataSourceAddress : String, json : String) : String {
54
55     var responseMessage : String
56
57     /* Data Source Example Address: "http://123.45.67.89:8000/make_image"
58 */
59
60     var url_command : String = dataSourceAddress
61
62     var response : Integer
63
64     if (url_command.equals("")) {
65         info("Access of AAS-Function Lock - TBD.")
66         return responseMessage
67     }
68
69     var url : URL = new URL(url_command)
70     var connection : HttpURLConnection = url.openConnection() as HttpURLConnection
71
72     connection.setDoOutput(true)
73     connection.setInstanceFollowRedirects(false)
74
75     connection.setRequestMethod("POST")
76     connection.setRequestProperty("Content-Type", "application/json")
77
78     connection.getOutputStream().write(json.getBytes("UTF-8"))
79
80     responseMessage = connection.getResponseMessage()
81
82     info("Response message for PRIO is: " + responseMessage)
83
    
```

Figure 56: Janus Skill for Quality Check Machine Learning Service ¹³

12 SARL IDE (Capacity Example for Quality Check Machine Learning Service)

13 SARL IDE (Implemented Skill Example for Quality Check Machine Learning Service)

The integration of the skill into the Janus agent behavior is shown in Figure 57. The Quality Check agent thus have two possibilities to implement the Quality Check interaction and control on asset-side, providing the interface for the OPC UA-Skill Model as well the interface for direct connection to the camera and the Quality Check Machine Learning Service by using REST.


```

213  /*
214     * Algorithm specific part
215     */
216
217     /* At first, build the command to get required data. */
218
219     datajson = BuildJSONCommandForInputData("")
220
221     /* Collect the data in a suitable format with required inputs. */
222     /* AAS-Structure from the AI agent itself, can be considered. */
223
224     dataset = DataCollection("", datajson)
225
226     /* Provide the dataset to the algorithmn. */
227
228     algojson = BuildJSONCommandForAlgorithm(dataset)
229
230     /* Get the result and work with it inside of the MAS. */
231
232     result = QualityAlgorithm("", algojson)
233
234
235     wake(new Skill_End)
236
237 }
238
  
```

The Outline pane on the right shows the project structure:

- agents
 - Quality_1
 - capacity uses
 - comspace : OpenEventSpace
 - agentname : String
 - on BehaviorInitialize
 - on Move
 - on Skill_Begin
 - on Skill_End
 - Quality_1_Algorithmn
 - capacity uses
 - comspace : OpenEventSpace
 - agentname : String
 - on BehaviorInitialize
 - on Move
 - on Skill_Begin
 - on Skill_End
 - Quality1
 - capacity uses
 - qualitySkill : QualitySkill
 - qualityAlgorithmSkill : QualityAlgorithmSkill

Figure 57: Skill implementation inside Quality Algorithm behaviour of a Quality Check Agent ¹⁴

The possibility to use the Janus Skills thus provides to switch between several interfaces in a manner, that integrations could be provided more flexible, based on the given components to collect data and to use them for algorithms and machine learning services.

¹⁴ SARL IDE (Skill usage inside of Quality Agent behaviour)

7.8 Summarized results

The prototypical implementations of the Smart Factory testbed environment of the first and second iteration on the respective demonstrators and the MAS4AI framework evaluation, the methodical approach for the development and the combined results are presented in this deliverable. The flexibility of the MAS4AI approach was demonstrated, considering the approach to use the AAS as possibility to switch between several middleware technologies like BaSyx or the Dimofac-Platform. The distributed holonic concept of the first iteration results was scaled to a Shared Production environment during the development of the second iteration results. The MAS4AI framework thus provides high modularity and is applicable to several technological data layers and hardware constellations. The flexibility has thus been demonstrated in the evaluation of several agent types, as presented in Table 28.

Agent	Input	Output	Status 1 st Iteration	Status 2 nd Iteration
Production module agent	Raw material	Processed material	Successful integration	Successful integration
Transport agent	Transported good	Transported good	Successful integration	Successful integration
Quality Inspection agent (ML)	Product	Product (+Quality assessment)	In Progress (AAS prepared)	Successful integration
Energy agent	Energy Signals	Energy Data and application	In Progress (AAS prepared)	Successful integration
AMS / HMI Agent	Agent System Events	Commands and Human Decisions	Not considered	Prototypical Implementation
Planning Agent (RL)	Factory state	Task assignment to machine	Not considered	Prototypical Implementation

Table 28: Status of integrated agents in the testbed environment (2nd iteration)

As in the first iteration results, the encapsulation of assets (hardware- or software-related) was also essential for the results during the second iteration. The availability of infrastructure-based components like Registry and Discovery was also applicable for the agent's self-description and for their interaction. The usage of Apache Kafka as message channel thus was evaluated successfully in various constellations, for example during the AMS prototype. The development of agent types in a template-related manner, as provided with the Janus SARL modeling, guaranteed a higher encapsulation and reusability for integration.

The agent types of both iterations could furthermore be used as suggestion for application in other pilot lines of the MAS4AI project and considers the first results of these (e.g., planning).

8 Conclusion of second iteration

The prototypical implementations of the MAS4AI framework of the first and second iteration presented the results in the SmartFactory-KL testbed. The importance of a modularized and encapsulated framework approach, which can thus be parametrized and configured has been demonstrated on the modular level with Cyber-Physical Production Systems in the first iteration as well as for the more software-specific parts like Machine Learning-Agents, Planning Agents as well as the AMS agent. The usage of the AAS for asset representation and interface provision, also for the MAS itself, was essential for the successful integration and interoperability. The interoperability of the data layer has thus been demonstrated, with the possibility to integrate AAS which are realized with the BaSyx-Middleware, the Dimofac-Platform with MQTT as well as directly with OPC UA.

The holonic approach of the MAS could be scaled up on a distributed factory layer, combining several production environments to produce several types of a product, as well scaled down to the level of modular modules with submodules. The usage of Apache Kafka was furthermore evaluated during the second iteration prototyping and further used as AMS message channel. Deployment possibilities in a distributed manner with the Docker technology has been realized.

The development of agent types in an encapsulated and pattern-oriented format as result of the first iteration results was useful to provide templates which could be adopted in the subsequent pilot line use cases in the project. Conversely, the results from the Work Packages 3-5 could be considered in the second iteration of the second iteration of the SmartFactory-KL. Especially the Machine Learning and Planning Agent-Concepts could thus be also evaluated in the demonstrator and new agent templates could be developed, especially for energy agents on the resource level as well for AMS agents with the BaSyx-Middleware and Dimofac-Platform. The integration of Human Operators for configuration, parametrization, and control of the system with respective information of agent states and lifecycles are thus provided within the AMS and graphical UI. For the agent type of an HMI agent conceptual preparations have been considered, for Human Smart Worker collaboration with a gripper robot, in which both are represented as agents in the MAS4AI system. Some agent types, for example Product Agents as well as Safety Agents are considered in less pilot lines of the MAS4AI project were realized specific and were not part of the second iteration.

Nevertheless, based on the overall results of the SmartFactory-KL testbed, there is potential for future research, as it has been prepared for the HMI agent as well for a further integration of semantic technologies in combination with the AAS. The provision of the results for the industrial Pilot Lines of MAS4AI and further developments will furthermore consider the presented results.

9 Literature

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